

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES OF COMPLEX ACID. PART II. CONDUCTOMETRIC AND GLASS ELECTRODE TITRATION OF MOLYBDIC ACID SOL

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Molybdic acid sol, prepared by the action of dilute hydrochloric acid on ammonium molybdate solution, when dialysed free from Cl⁻ ion, has a composition of the solute corresponding to NH₄E-[O(MoO₃)₄]. The sol on dilution from 3.30 × 10⁻³ M-MoO₃ to 1.65 × 10⁻⁴ M-MoO₃ gave continually increasing value of p_a. In the region of p_a 3.8 to 4.5, the curve was rather flat and this has been ascribed to the disintegration of colloidal micelle of molybdic acid to true solution containing simpler ions as HMoO₄' etc. The dissociation constant of this acid ion HMoO₄' has been calculated to be p_a = 6.33 from the potentiometric titration curve of the sol with NaOH.

Though molybdenum and tungsten occur in the same group of the periodic table as sulphur and chromium and form well defined normal salts as Na₂MoO₄, the corresponding molybdic and tungstic acids do not resemble H₂SO₄ or H₂CrO₄ in any other respects, and show abnormal changes in p_a and conductivity during neutralisation.

Travers and Malaprade (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1929, 39, 1406, 1543) investigated the course of neutralisation of molybdic acid solution with KOH electrometrically and suggested the presence of tetramolybdic acid in solution from the observation of an inflexion in the curve at 1/4 equivalent of the acid. Bevan (Britton, "Hydrogen Ions", 1940, Vol. I, p. 224) came to the same conclusion from similar electrometric studies and assumed the acid ionising as,

during neutralisation. Chatelain (*Compt. rend.*, 1939, 208, 584) got the same nature of curves as Travers (*loc. cit.*) and Honnelaitre (*Ann. Chim.*, 1925, 3, 31) but interpreted her results on the assumption that dimolybdic acid in solution ionised thus,

The above mechanism supported her previous works on the absorption spectra of MoO₃ solution (*Compt. rend.*, 1937, 205, 222; 1938, 206, 669) when the presence of only one kind of molybdate ion responsible for absorption was found.

The apparently controversial ideas, as revealed, are due to the fact that the polyphasic character of the system was not taken into consideration; it was thought that the equilibrium of the system in all stages of reaction was governed by the law of mass action as applicable to homogeneous systems. The investigations of Rosenheim and Bertheim (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1903, 34, 427; 1906, 54, 320) and Dhar and collaborators (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 184, 135) have shown that molybdic acid in its aqueous solution is present partly as a colloid and partly as true solution and Dhar and collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1943, 20, 282) grouped it as "colloidal electrolytes" due to its similarity in behaviour with soap solution (McBain, 1920). The carefully dialysed molybdic

acid salt, as we have obtained under conditions stated in Part I, was found by ultramicroscopic examination to contain a considerable number of colloidal particles (10^8 per c.c. for 0.02 *M*- MoO_3 sol) and the mean composition of the solute was shown to correspond with the formula $\text{NH}_4\text{H}[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_4]$. The likely equilibrium condition existing can possibly be represented as:—

The measurement of conductivity and $[\text{H}^+]$ at different dilutions of the sol may indicate the existence and the nature of transformation of such equilibrium.

Following Duclaux (*J. chim. phys.*, 1909, 7, 405), Michaelis (*Biochem. Z.*, 1920, 106, 83), Pauli and Valkó ("Electrochemie der Kolloide", 1929) and McBain (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 426; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 706) we are led to believe that colloidal solutions of electrolytic substances should be treated as counterparts of electrolytes in true solution and equilibrium condition arising in any stage of the system is governed by the law of mass action just like substances in true solution. But Mukherjee and collaborators (*Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, 227) questioned the validity of such assumptions in certain cases and illustrated the difficulties encountered in the studies of a number of colloidal systems like silicic acid, palmitic acid, MnO , etc., and some sparingly soluble organic acids like cinnamic acid, etc., in interpreting the electrometric titration curves of such heterogeneous acid systems. Accordingly the electrometric titration curves should be analysed and interpreted with caution paying the due attention to the polyphasic character of the system.

The object of the present investigation is to study critically the course of electrometric titration curves of the neutralisation of molybdic acid sol with NaOH , and to determine the nature of its ionisations at different stages.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The conductometric and glass electrode titration methods were the same as described in Part I (*this issue*, p. 228). The preparation of a well-dialysed molybdic acid sol from NH_4 -molybdate and HCl was also described there. The effect of ageing for 48 hours or heating at 85° for 20 minutes after each addition of NaOH was also observed as before.

Conductometric and Potentiometric Titrations

In Fig. 1 (curve 1) are represented graphically the results of conductometric titration of 50 c.c. of 2.545×10^{-2} *M*- MoO_3 sol (according to gravimetric estimation) with 0.703 *N*- NaOH . The corresponding potentiometric results are shown similarly in curve 2. The dotted lines represent the course when readings were taken immediately after mixing of the added titre, the continuous lines being for readings taken after heating and cooling to 25° . The data from the ageing experiments are not shown because they have more or less intermediate values.

It will be noticed that heating after each addition of the titre influences the course of the curves only in the first portion but later both types of curves coincide. In curve 2, it is seen that p_s values rapidly increase in the beginning as if free H^+ ions are being

FIG. 1

removed ; after that the curve shows slightly undulating region ; beyond that it assumed the nature of the neutralisation of a weak acid ending with a sharp inflexion. We, thus, observe here two inflexions and the data from a number of such titration curves are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Mols of MoO_3 present.	Mols of NaOH corresponding to		Calc. Mols of NaOH from eq. (5).
	1st inflexion.	2nd inflexion.	
4.243×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-4}	7.60×10^{-4}	7.425×10^{-4}
7.065	2.00	12.60	12.36
8.875	2.35	15.85	15.43
12.790	3.37	22.29	22.38
17.820	4.95	32.10	31.19

The 1st inflexions are approximately 1/7 of the 2nd inflexion values in all cases. The volumetric titration with the same amount of the sol, carried out separately using phenolphthalein as indicator, showed that the titre values coincided with the 2nd inflexion values. Leaving the question of the 1st inflexion for later discussion, the reaction of the solute of the MoO_3 sol with NaOH, corresponding to 2nd inflexion, can be represented by the following stoichiometric equation,

The NaOH equivalent calculated from this equation agreed well as shown in Table I.

Referring to the corresponding conductometric curve in Fig. 1 (curve 1) it is found that conductivity diminishes rapidly in the beginning, passes through a sharp minimum and then it increases to a maximum, followed by a small, nearly flat region where conductivity tends to diminish and then again increases very rapidly as would be the case if free NaOH were present. We, thus, observe here 3 breaks, our experimental data corresponding to the three breaks are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Mols of MoO ₃ .	Mols of NaOH calc from eqn. (%)	Mols of NaOH from 1st break.	Mols of NaOH from 2nd break.	Mols of NaOH from 3rd break.	Diff. between 3rd and 2nd breaks.	Estimated Mols of NH ₃ (Kjeldahl method).
4.243 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.486 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.15 × 10 ⁻⁴	7.50 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.55 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.05 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.032 × 10 ⁻⁴
7.065	14.13	1.90	12.50	14.40	1.90	1.760
8.872	17.74	2.25	15.75	18.50	2.05	2.22
12.79	25.58	3.30	22.28	25.35	3.07	3.20
17.82	35.64	4.50	31.50	33.10	4.60	4.45

FIG. 2

Comparing these values with those in Table I, it is seen that the 1st and 2nd breaks fairly coincide with the 1st and 2nd inflexion values of the potentiometric curves. Obviously their occurrences are due to the same reaction, the existence of the 2nd break is to be associated with equation (i) above. The observed flat region and the 3rd break can be represented by an equation,

The NaOH equivalents calculated from this equation, as seen in Table II, agree well with the values from 3rd breaks. Moreover, the amount resulting from the difference between the 3rd and 2nd breaks should be equivalent to the quantity of NH_3 present in the solution. These calculated values are actually of the same order as those estimated by the Kjeldahl method.

p_n of MoO_3 Sol at different Dilutions

The carefully purified sol (0.033 M - MoO_3) is diluted with conductivity water to different extents in separate glass-stoppered bottles and allowed to stand for 48 hours at room temperature (25°). The p_n values are then measured and the results are presented graphically in Fig. 2, where the p_n values of the diluted sols are plotted against the log of different dilutions.

DISCUSSION

If we assume that molybdic acid in sols or solutions ultimately behaves as dibasic $\text{H}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_2]$ during neutralisation, two moles of NaOH per atom of molybdenum are necessary for complete neutralisation. The potentiometric and conductometric results (Tables I and II) showed definitely that 7/8 of the total Mo was available for neutralisation as normal dibasic acid forming $\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_2]$ and the rest remained associated with the NH_3 present in the sol as $(\text{NH}_3)_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_2]$. When still more NaOH was added, reaction took place as

It will be seen in Tables I and II that the 1st inflexion or break of the respective potentiometric or conductometric curves occurs roughly when one mole of NaOH per mole of $\text{NH}_3\text{H}[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_2]$ was added and this can be qualitatively represented by an equation,

The region of the potentiometric curve beyond the 1st inflexion is due to the process of transformation of the polyacidic anions existing as colloidal particles or micelles into simpler ones and this extends until the alkali equivalent to the one-half of the acid available for neutralisation, is added. The solution at this stage and after, contains the acid molybdate ion (HMoO_4') in true solution (near about p_n 5.0) and with further addition of NaOH, the curve assumes the nature of the neutralisation of a weak acid. The nature of ionisations during the 1st half of the neutralisation curve can be represented as follows :

Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) analysed the applicability of the relationships existing in the case of true solution to heterophase systems and found the mass law to be inapplicable in such cases since the mass of the acid in the interior of the colloidal particles or micelles are unavailable for equilibrium with the dissolved acid in the intermicellar liquid and the kinetics of the surface reaction was found to play a definite role. Therefore, the degree

of dissociation, dissociation constant, solubility and similar other magnitudes have a sense different from that in true electrolytic systems. Accordingly, it is meaningless to attempt to determine the reaction equilibrium as indicated in the above or to suggest, as was done by previous workers, the presence of any definite polyacid such as tetra or dimolybdic acids from inflexions or breaks observed in electrometric curves so long as the system is heterogeneous. But beyond p_n 5.0, i.e. in the 2nd half of the potentiometric curve, we can safely assume the applicability of the mass law for the reaction equilibrium

when

$$K = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{MoO}_4'']}{[\text{HMoO}_4']}$$

In Table III below we have calculated some of the p_k values from the potentiometric titration curve in the region above p_n 5.0.

TABLE III

NaOH.	p_n .	p_k .
1.10 equiv.	5.38	6.33
1.15	5.50	6.32
1.20	5.62	6.33
1.25	5.67	6.25
1.30	5.79	6.16

The p_k values are fairly constant showing the validity of our assumptions.

The p_n -dilution curve reveals how high molecular colloidal polymolybdic acid gradually goes into true solution. The p_n values remain almost steady, like a buffer solution when the dilution is increased from 200 to 2000 times. With progressive dilution in this region (p_n 3.8, concentration of the MoO_3 sol $1.65 \times 10^{-4} M$) p_n values change much more slowly than would be expected from an acid in true solution, because of the transformation of colloidal polymeric anions into simpler ones which generate H^+ in the process. This process becomes complete, i.e. practically all the particles pass into true solution after dilution to 2000 times (p_n 4.5, concentration of the sol = $1.65 \times 10^{-5} M$ - MoO_3). As the dilution is increased further, values of p_n increase as would be the case with a weak acid.